

**Cross-cutting activity 1:
Support to the generation and
the development of start-ups
and spin-offs**

— Open Innovation activities

**Leader:
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1. INTRODUCTION TO THE CROSS-CUTTING ACTIVITY 1 GOALS AND ACTIVITIES

(A cura del coordinatore dell'attività trasversale)

2. OPEN INNOVATION ACTIVITIES within the cross-cutting activity 1

The Open Innovation activity, included in the cross-cutting activity CCI aims to facilitate the intersection between the solutions proposed by startups and spinoffs from academia and the innovation needs of the business world.

2.1. RESEARCH OF OPEN INNOVATION BEST PRACTICES IN ACADEMIA

The survey initially focused on identifying the main strategic approaches to Open Innovation and identifying best practices in the Italian university environment. The goal was to formulate an Open Innovation action plan for the iNEST project.

Regarding approaches to Open Innovation, the following were identified: Inbound Open Innovation approach, whereby the company acquires external ideas, technologies, and expertise to meet innovation needs, such as developing new products and services; Outbound Open Innovation, whereby the company provides for the commercialization or exploitation of internal resources, such as patents, technologies, or expertise, through partnerships or licenses with other organizations.

Best practices in academia were then categorized into three macro models:

- Call4solution: collection of innovation needs followed by solution scouting through publication of an internal call or search, followed by matching and project development.
- Lab: identification of challenges by companies coming from innovation needs; search for solutions within the initiative by teams of selected students/researchers, trained by the university and assigned to the company to work on the needs.
- Matching Platform: model not tied to specific project timelines, with the aim of providing visible opportunities for collaboration to target entities.

2.2. DEFINITION OF AN ACTION PLAN FOR OPEN INNOVATION

Based on the survey on Open Innovation best practices and the pre-acceleration program shared by the CCI activity coordinator, an action plan for Open Innovation in the iNEST project was proposed, subsequently shared in a meeting on 27 October in the presence of the coordinator of the CCI activity.

The action plan, revised following the meeting on 27 October, provides for a mapping of companies in the Triveneto in two phases, with large numbers in the first step and small numbers in the second. The mapped companies will be recruited following the pre-acceleration process, so that the solutions identified here can be cross-referenced with the companies' innovation needs.

2.3. RECRUITING INNOVATION-ORIENTED COMPANIES FIRST STEP

Bureau van Dijk's AIDA program was chosen among various options as a tool for mapping companies in the Triveneto area in the first step of the mapping. This tool allows access to the data of the statutory financial statements of Italian companies, including for example the R&D costs incurred and patent rights, allowing the identification of the companies in the Triveneto area most oriented towards innovation and therefore potentially interested in solutions coming from pre-acceleration program.

At the moment, a first version of the methodology to be used for mapping has been defined. This includes the following key points:

- selection of companies in the Triveneto area based on dimensional parameters;
- definition of performance indicators starting from budget data;
- division of companies into homogeneous groups by size and sector;
- evaluation of the innovation performance of companies within homogeneous groups, based on the indicators identified.

2.4. DETECTING OPPORTUNITIES FOR OPEN INNOVATION IN SCOUTING ACTIVITIES

The Spoke 3 scouting specialist was supported in the scouting activities related to the University of Udine, with the aim of identifying solutions to match with the needs of the companies that will subsequently be involved. The results of this activity will be shared with those of the other Spokes, in order to identify, together with the coordinator of the CCI action, activities and procedures to be introduced in the second pre-acceleration cycle, in order to facilitate the Open Innovation process in the iNEST project.